

Globalisation and the spread of English

Ro'zixon Yoqubjonova

Akbarova Diyora

Andijon Davlat Chet Tillari Instituti

Dealing with the first part of the threefold framework suggested in the outline is not a simple matter.

After reviewing the huge amount of literature that exists I decided to start by giving the historical

context and by introducing important terminology. After that I present two opposing "world-views" on

the subject, exemplified by Phillipson's Linguistic Imperialism (1992) and Crystal's English as a global

language (1997). Other issues involved will be explored with this framework in mind. Torn between the

desire to tackle all the issues and the necessity of presenting a clear argument I have compiled an

additional bibliography of works which cannot be dealt with in the main text because of restrictions of

space, because of lack in overall relevance and because I do not feel that it is useful to make "one book

out of twenty". This additional bibliography is given in Appendix A.

In 1914 Follick envisioned the global spread of a simplified form of English.

Today, his vision has been

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enormously surpassed: English (with all its idiosyncrasies) is used as the global language - spoken in all fields which require international contact and co-operation (for a list see Crystal 1997: 8). It therefore makes sense to give a short historical sketch of how this "spreading"¹ of the language happened.² The foundations for the expansion of English were laid as the British Empire itself expanded (roughly between 1600 and 1900). English and English Language Teaching (ELT) served as a tool to strengthen.

English in the education system: In the current system, English is already taught in primary school. How

this should be done has given rise to some debate, even in parliament. In a session dedicated to

educational policy the conservative position was voiced by a member of the Freedom Party (Monika

Muhlwert) who was of the opinion that it is essential for pupils at primary school to have a native

speaker teacher; she argued strongly against primary school teachers who teach English "with a certain

Ottakiring [a Viennese district] accent". At the time these arguments were criticized by G,

¹ For a discussion of the notions of "spread" versus "distribution" see Widdowson (1997:136- 140).

² See also Crystal (1997) and Pennycook (1994, 1998). Bailey (1991) provides valuable insights into how the attitudes connected with English have changed in the course of time

Leichdfried (Social Democrats), who saw the teaching of English in primary schools as a step in the right direction if it is done in a playful manner, and Uta P,hringer (Conservatives), who (very rightly) pointed out that it is most important that the children are able to communicate in English, not what accent they speak (stenographisches Protokoll Bundesrat 1998: i, my translation). Mayer (1995: 62) holds that the EFL approach in primary school should be explicitly monolingual. At secondary schools English is an obligatory subject taught between 3 and 5 hours per week (Hebenstreit 1998: 35). The officially prescribed goals are that the pupils should be able to understand authentic³ written and spoken texts and learn to express themselves appropriately. However communicative competence was never the sole objective. While the 1961 curriculum specified that EFL should also teach pupils objectivity, industriousness, distance and the recognition of authority (Malzacher 1996: 57) nowadays modern languages are meant to promote tolerance of other cultures, to broaden the pupils' horizons

References

³ For a criticism of the notion of authenticity see ch.1.4.1. and Seidlhofer (1995)

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2. Brown, Kimberley (1995) World English: to teach or not to teach?" World English 14/2 233- 245
3. Bryson, Bill (1990) Mother Tongue. The English Language. London: Penguin
- 4.Crystal, David (1997) English as a global Language. Cambridg: CUP.
5. English Language Satellite Broadcasts over Europe.
http://www3.mistral.co.uk/bradleyw/eng_eur.htm